

Search for Potential Herbicides. Synthesis of Nitrophenyl-2-cyanoacrylamides

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Among the various factors which effect the yield of a crop, timely control of weeds plays an important role. Chemicals frequently applied for weed control are butachlor, methabenzthiauron, metaxuron, nitrofen etc. These compounds possess heterocyclic system, amide linkage and substituted phenyl ring.

In continuation of our earlier work¹ on the synthesis of new chemicals and exploring their possibility for use as broad spectrum herbicides, efforts have been made to synthesise compounds incorporating cyano group, amide linkage and aliphatic/heterocyclic system.

2-Cyano-3-(2', 3'- and 4'-nitro-1'-phenyl)acrylic acids (1a—c) were obtained by treatment of cyanoacetic acid with the corresponding nitrobenzaldehyde using pyridine and piperidine as base. Reaction of 2-cyano-3-(2'-nitro-1'-phenyl)acrylic acid with cyclohexylamine, morpholine and 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolene-5-one in the presence of triethylamine/ POCl_3 produced the corresponding amides (2a—c). Adopting the same procedure, 2-cyano-3-(3'-nitro-1'-phenyl)acrylic acid and 2-cyano-3-(4'-nitro-1'-phenyl)acrylic acid were treated with cyclohexylamine, morpholine and 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolene-5-one, compounds 2d—i were obtained. Their structures were confirmed by ir and nmr spectra² (Table 1). The presence of NH protons was confirmed by D_2O exchange.

Compounds 2a—i were tested³ for herbicidal activity against *Echinochloa crus-galli* and *Trianthema postulaacastrum* at concentrations 0, 100, 200, 300,

400 and 500 ppm. Compounds having nitro group at *ortho*-position in phenyl ring showed highest activity. Activity decreased as the nitro group moved from *ortho* to *para* position through *meta*. Among the amides carrying cyclohexyl, morpholine and pyrazolene system, the latter enhanced activity to a greater extent.

1a; R = 2-NO₂

1b; R = 3-NO₂

1c; R = 4-NO₂

2a-c, R = 2-NO₂; 2a, d, g; R' =

2d-f; R = 3-NO₂; 2b, e, h; R' =

2g-i; R = 4-NO₂; 2c, f, i; R' =

NOTES

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	δ (CDCl ₃)
1a	138–42	59	3 160, 2 240, 1 620, 1 525, 970	—
b	124–26	68	3 120, 2 230, 1 620, 1 635, 960, 810	—
c	205–07	73	3 140, 2 235, 1 630, 960, 820	—
2a	98–100	33	3 340, 2 240, 1 665, 1 570, 965, 720	8.75 (s, olefinic H), 7.8–7.6 (m, Ar H), 6.3 (bs, exchangeable, NH), 2.1–1.1 (m, cyclohexyl H)
b	74–76	30	3 420, 2 210, 1 635, 1 090, 996, 855, 789	7.98 (s, olefinic H), 7.8 (m, ArH), 3.8 (m, methylene H)
c	206–08	40	3 240, 2 230, 1 660, 1 620, 1 380, 940, 862	3.23 (s, N-CH ₃), 2.45 (s, O=C=C=C-CH ₃), 8.65 (s, HC=CCN), 7.2–8.3 (9H, m, ArH), 8.4 (s, NHCO)
d	114–18	28	3 360, 2 210, 1 670, 1 530, 1 030, 930, 810, 730	6.25 (s, NHCO), 7.5–7.8 (m, ArH), 8.65 (s, HC=CCN), 1.2–2.2 (m, methylene H)
e	138–40	59	3 320, 2 220, 1 640, 1 538, 1 020, 945, 815, 740	1.6 (4H, m, CH ₂ OCH ₂), 3.8 (m, CH ₂ -NCH ₂)
f	195–97	45	3 360, 2 220, 1 650, 1 535, 1 310, 810	2.3 (s, NCH ₃), 3.16 (s, O=C=C=C-CH ₃), 7.35–8.3 (9H, m, ArH), 9.3 (s, -CH=CCN), 8.5 (s, NHCO)
g	208–09	35	3 320, 2 225, 1 650, 1 540, 1 310, 815	6.20 (s, NHCO), 7.5–7.7 (m, ArH), 8.60 (s, HC-CCN), 1.0–2.1 (m, methylene H)
h	230–31	42	3 440, 2 220, 1 655, 1 545, 1 310, 820	7.85 (s, CH-CCN), 3.75 (m, N)
i	215–17	40	3 300, 2 220, 1 670	7.8 (m, ArH) 1.6 (s, O=C=C-CH ₃), 2.8 (3H, s, N-CH ₃), 7.3 (1H, s, HC=CCN), 7.5–7.7 (9H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, NH-CO)

Experimental

All m.ps./b.ps. are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 800 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra on a EM/390 (90 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra (70 eV) on a VG-Analytical-11-2505-70-S spectrometer.

2-Cyano-3-(nitro substituted-1'-phenyl)acrylic acids (1a–c). *General procedure:* A mixture of cyanoacetic acid (0.025 mol), piperidine (1 ml), pyridine (2 ml) and appropriate nitrobenzaldehyde (0.025 mol) in benzene (200 ml) was refluxed using Dean and Stark apparatus for 10 h in an oil-bath. It was then cooled, washed with water, dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate), solvent evaporated and the residue was purified by recrystallisation from ethanol.

N-Substituted-2-cyano-3-(2'/3'/4'-nitro-1'-phenyl)acrylamide (2a–i). *General procedure:* To a well-stirred mixture of 2-cyano-3-(nitro-1'-phenyl)acrylic acid (0.025 mol) in dry dichloromethane (50 ml) and the corresponding amine (0.025 mol) dissolved in dry dichloromethane (25 ml) and triethylamine (0.008 mol), was added a solution of phosphorus oxychloride (0.025 mol) in dichloromethane (20 ml) dropwise through dropping funnel. Another instalment of triethylamine (0.008 mol) was added in one

lot. The contents were stirred at 0° for 0.5 h and for another 6 h at room temperature. Progress of the reaction was checked on tlc plates at regular intervals. The reaction mixture was then decomposed in crushed ice and extracted with dichloromethane. The organic portion was washed with saturated solution of sodium carbonate (3 × 20 ml), water, HCl (10%, 3 × 20 ml) and finally with water. After drying the organic portion over anhydrous CaCl₂, the solvent was evaporated and the residue was chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-chloroform (1 : 3) as eluent to obtain pure products.

References

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